

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. D.3.3

Nomination and launch of the Polar Expert Group

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 3 Research Prioritisation
Deliverable No	D.3.3
Deliverable title	Nomination and launch of the Polar Expert Group
Version	Final version
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	DAFSHE
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - NWO, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 –IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – SPI
Coordinating author	Stine Djørup
Contributing authors	AWI
Due date	31.07.2021
Delivery date	13.08.2021

Document history	
Creation Date	
Revision	V1
Revision Date	04.08.2021
Author	DAFSHE
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	04.08.2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY 4

1 Introduction 5

2 Nomination Procedure 6

3 Launch of the PEG 7

4 All Nominees 7

7. Statistics 18

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

This Deliverable presents the process for the nomination and launch of the Polar Expert Group (PEG). The PEG is intended to be a group of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research within the EU-PolarNet 2 project, and in particular within 11 defined polar research disciplines. This activity is part of the objective of advancing European polar research strategies and supporting the development of large-scale international polar initiatives carried out by WP3. The process here presented is organised in different sections, including selection criteria and nomination procedure, list of all nominees and list of executive PEG.

1 Introduction

The Polar Expert Group (PEG) is intended to be a group of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research, including different sector representatives. The main aim of the PEG is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar Research themes on the basis of the European Polar Research program (EPRP), the White Paper and the European Polar strategies, also integrating stake and rights-holders' interests, both at Arctic and Antarctic level. For this reason, the PEG will be a tool for bringing Research Prioritisation to the future European Polar Coordination Office (EPCO).

The internal architecture of the PEG will be organised as a twofold structure, consisting of an Executive PEG surrounded by a larger groups of experts consisting of 200 experts. The members of the Executive PEG will act as representatives of their research disciplines and be directly involved in the research prioritisation and evaluation of Service Call proposals. The Executive PEG will also be the ones mostly interacting with the MST. The Executive PEG will be supported by the larger groups of experts that will act as support in the research prioritisation work, but who will only be contacted for very specific questions which are also mediated through the Executive PEG.

The PEG's responsibilities include:

- Specifying and customising the research needs for the research community proposed in the EPRP and in the EU-PolarNet 1 White Papers.
- Formulating achievable research actions to be carried out in the future.
- Promoting large-scale Polar research initiatives by integrating the outcomes of transdisciplinary workshops and the findings of bottom-up scouting initiatives.
- Contributing to the selection process through Service Contract calls.

The PEG directly interacts with all the WPs of the project:

1. WP1 will assure that inputs from the European Polar communities will trigger the research prioritisation process enacted by the PEG.
2. WP2 will ensure meaningful stakeholder involvement with inputs for the research prioritisation process enacted by the PEG.
3. WP3 will define the overarching research areas based on recommendations from the PEG.
4. WP4 will facilitate implementation of the ideas and proposals developed by the PEG and in WP3 by the funding agencies.
5. WP5 will be fed with the PEG's results on research prioritisation. WP5 in particular, will translate these outputs so they are useful for policymaking (supporting policy briefings).
6. WP6 is responsible to build the EPCO, for which the PEG represents one of the tools for research prioritisation.

2 Nomination Procedure

Within the first step of the selection procedure all the EU-PolarNet2 Partners were invited to nominate experts for up to 11 different polar research disciplines which originated from [EU-PolarNet 2 D2.1](#) and reflected the European Polar research priorities. Partners were invited to nominate up to two experts per research field, one with Arctic the other one with Antarctic expertise. It was not mandatory to nominate experts for all disciplines.

In a second step a 1st shortlist of preferred candidates for each of the research themes was established by the EU-PolarNet 2 Executive Board and the responsible partners of WP3.

The selection was based on the following criteria listed here by importance:

- Scientific expertise and excellence
- Candidates who have an in-depth overview of their community and area of expertise
- Balance Arctic/Antarctic, or people who are clearly working at both poles.
- National balance between European countries (some countries have a greater strength in the Arctic, other in the Antarctic)
- Candidates who are taking their duties seriously and can spend enough time for the PEG.
- Early Career Researchers should be given priority if they have an appropriate expertise.
- Gender balance
- Balance between people who were involved in the EU-PolarNet 1 EPRP and White Paper process, and new members.

After a discussion of the first shortlist in an online meeting, a 2nd shortlist using the same criteria was identified in a third step. From the second list the 22 PEG Executive members - who are act as representatives of their research discipline - were selected by the Executive Board and the responsible WP3 partners. In this process, nominees with cross-cutting and complementary expertise were added to the group as additional members. It was also decided to allow more than two PEG members for those themes which are probably in the core of the research prioritisation process due to current EC and national Polar strategies. The final list of the Executive PEG members will be available at the EU-PolarNet website in fall 2021, link: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/consortium-structure/>

The remaining group of the nominees are to be engaged as the large group of 200 experts from which the Executive PEG may draw upon in their work.

3 Launch of the PEG

The actual work with and engagement of the executive PEG, as well as the full expert group, will be launched as followed: The selected core members of the executive PEG are invited by email by the coordinator. In addition, a videoconference/webinar with the full expert group will be scheduled for September 2021 to introduce EU-PolarNet 2 them and to describe how the group will be involved in EU-PolarNet 2 and what the workload will be.

4 All Nominees

The 11 European Polar Research Priorities were developed in EU-PolarNet 1, by studies based on publications of national Polar Strategies, international consortia, and major scientific clusters. Based on this work, an on-line consultation was launched to integrate the science community's input into the compilation of research priorities and related societal challenges.

For each of these 11 European Polar Research Priorities (D2.1 EU-PolarNet) 1 the EU-PolarNet 2 project partners designated up to two candidate experts renowned in their research fields, one focussing on the Arctic and another on the Antarctic. The nominated experts are listed below sorted by the research priorities for which they are can provide expertise.

1. Polar Climate Systems

This research discipline address the natural processes in the Polar Regions that influence or control conditions across the globe, as well as changes in Polar Regions that have global importance for people, policy and businesses well beyond the Polar Regions.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Christensen Røjle, Torben	Danish	Aarhus University	Arctic
Colleoni, Florence	Italian	OGS	Antarctic
Fransson, Agneta	Swedish	Norwegian Polar Institute	Both poles
González Herrero, Sergi	Spanish	Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET)	Antarctic
Hattermann, Tore	German	Norwegian Polar Institute	Antarctic, Both poles
Hugues Goosse	Belgian	Université catholique de Louvain	Antarctic
Huybrechts Philippe	Belgian	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Both poles
Jong de, Femke	Dutch	NIOZ, Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea research	Arctic
Jaagus, Jaak	Estonian	University of Tartu	Arctic
Komorin Viktor	Ukraine	NASC, UkrSCES	Antarctic
Krinner, Gerhard	German	CNRS, IGE, Grenoble, France	Both poles
Łupikasza Ewa	Polish	University of Silesia in Katowice, Institute of Earth Sciences	Arctic
Mazzola, Mauro	Italian	CNR-ISP	Arctic
Milnevsky Gennadi	Ukraine	National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine	Antarctic
Olsen M. , Steffen	Danish	Danish Meteorological Institute	Arctic
Ortega, Pablo	Spanish	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	Arctic
Rex, Markus	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Both poles
Schyberg, Harald	Norwegian	Norwegian Meteorological Institute	Arctic
Smedsrud, Lars Henrik	Norwegian	University of Bergen & Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research	Both poles
Swingedouw, Didier	French	CNRS, EPOC, Bordeaux	Arctic
Tørseth, Kjetil	Norwegian	NILU – Norwegian Institute for Air Research	Both poles
Wendisch, Manfred	German	Leipzig University	Arctic

2. Cryosphere

The main objective is to improve the understanding of factors associated with or contributing to the instability of ice sheets and global sea-level rise. These systems poses particular challenges to science, but is essential to manage the risks to coastal communities, precious coastal ecosystems and major capital assets across the globe. Governments, businesses and individuals who own, or are charged with protecting these assets, need to work more with science to inform their decisions on investment in and management of coastal regions.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Berthier, Etienne	French	CNRS, LEGOS, Toulouse	Both poles
Colgan, William	Canadian	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	Both poles
Frezzotti, Massimo	Italian	UNIROMA3	Antarctic
Hattermann, Tore	German	Norwegian Polar Institute	Antarctic, Both poles
Holmlund, Per	Swedish	Stockholm University	Both poles
Huybrechts Philippe	Belgian	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Both poles
Ignatiuk Dariusz	Polish	1) University of Silesia, Poland 2) SIOS Knowledge Centre, Norway	Arctic
Jari Haapala	Finnish	Finnish Meteorological Institute	Both poles
Macelloni, Giovanni	Italian	CNR-IFAC	Arctic
Oktar, Ozgun	Turkish	TUBITAK MAM Polar Research Institute	Both poles
Oliva, Marc	Spanish	Universitat de Barcelona	Both poles
Pattyn Frank	Belgian	Université Libre de Bruxelles	Antarctic
Pohjola, Veijo	Swedish	Uppsala University	Arctic
Rampal, Pierre	French	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center	Both poles
Rysgaard, Søren	Danish	Aarhus University	Arctic
Smetsrud, Lars Henrik	Norwegian	University of Bergen & Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research	Both poles
Vaikmäe, Rein	Estonian	Department of geology, Tallinn University of Technology	Both poles
van der Wal, Roderik	Dutch	IMAU - University of Utrecht	Both poles
Vieira, Gonçalo	Portuguese	Centro de Estudos Geográficos, IGOT - University of Lisbon, Portugal	Both poles
Weikusat, Ilka	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Arctic

3. Palaeoclimate and Palaeoenvironment

Future climate scenarios strongly benefit from paleo-reconstructions conducted in both Polar Regions as they allow a better understanding of how the climate system worked both regionally and globally during abrupt climatic transitions and under warmer or colder than present-day conditions. The main objectives thus address the use of paleo-reconstructions, including volcanic events, for projecting future climate scenarios, how paleo-records can provide key insight into changes under natural and anthropogenic forcing, and the understanding of the transition from 40ka cycles to 100ka cycles as crucial topic to understand current climate.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Lohmann, Gerrit	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Both poles
Herzschuh, Ulrike	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Arctic
FLORES, José-Abel	Spanish	Department of Geology. Universidad de Salamanca	Both poles
Escutia, Carlota	Spanish	Spanish Research Council (CSIC)	Antarctic
LANDAIS, Amaelle	French	CNRS, LSCE, Saclay	Both poles
HENRY, Auréade	French	CNRS, CEPAM, Nice	Arctic
Pawłowska Joanna	Polish	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland	Arctic
Majewski Wojciech	Polish	Institute of Paleobiology Polish Academy of Sciences	Antarctic
Veski, Siim	Estonian	IGTUT	Arctic
Goose Hugues	Belgian	Université catholique de Louvain	Antarctic
Verleyen Elie	Belgian	Universiteit Gent	Both poles
Dalén, Love	Swedish	Stockholm University	Arctic
Mörs, Thomas	Swedish	Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet	Antarctic
Ribeiro, Sophia	Portuguese	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Glaciology and Climate Department	Arctic
Kjellerup Kjeldsen , Kristian	Danish	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	Both poles
Risebrobakken, Bjørg	Norwegian	NORCE - Norwegian Research Centre	Arctic
Thomas, Liz	UK	BAS	TBA
Tesi, Tommaso	Italian	CNR-ISP	Arctic
del Monte, Barbara	Italian	Milano Bicocca	Antarctic

4. Polar Biology, Ecology and Biodiversity

The polar areas remain extremely stressful to organisms. The polar species, most of them exhibiting a high degree of endemism, are often close to their threshold of growth and have developed highly sophisticated adaptations which make them more vulnerable to rapid environmental changes. Therefore, the main objectives address threats to highly specialised and adapted polar species from climate-related changes in ecosystems, methods to identify and track the occurrence of invasive species and their impacts on ecosystems, methods to identify novel active compounds and processes for biotechnological and biomedical applications (bioprospecting), and the occurrence, severity, and impacts of ocean acidification.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
John, Uwe	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Arctic
Meyer, Bettina	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Antarctic
De los Ríos, Asunción	spanish	Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales-CSIC	Both poles
Avila, Conxita	Catalan (Spanish)	University of Barcelona	Antarctic
Erkinaro, Jaakko	Finnish	Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)	Arctic
Colnelissen, Hans	Dutch	Free University Amsterdam	Arctic
Bokhorst, Stef	Dutch	Free University Amsterdam	Both poles
Loonen, Maarten	Dutch	University of Groningen - Arctic Centre	Arctic
FORT, Jerome	French	CNRS, LIENSs, La Rochelle	Arctic
CHAUVAUD, Laurent	French	CNRS, LEMAR, Plouzané	Both poles
Błachowiak-Samołyk Katarzyna	Polish	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences	Both poles
Wojczulanis-Jakubas Katarzyna	Polish	University of Gdańsk	Both poles
Kaup Enn	Estonian	IGTUT	Both poles
Danis Bruno	Belgian	Université Libre de Bruxelles	Antarctic
Wilmotte Annick	Belgian	Université de Liège	Both poles
Axelsson, Michael	Swedish	Gothenburg University	Both poles
Snoeijs, Pauline	Swedish/Dutch	Stockholm University	Arctic
Kroer, Niels	Danish	University of Copenhagen	Arctic
Christoffersen, Kirsten	Danish	University of Copenhagen	Arctic
Berge, Jørgen	Norwegian	University of Tromsø - The Arctic University of Norway	Arctic, Both poles
Azzaro, Maurizio	Italian	CNR-ISP	Antarctic
Lo Guidice, Angelina	Italian	CNR-ISP	Arctic
Prekrasna Ievgeniia	Ukrainian	National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine	Antarctic

5. Human Impacts

Long-range transported pollutants and bioaccumulation of contaminants in polar food chains represent major challenges for both ecosystems and human health. Due to the increase in maritime operations and transport in the Arctic, a larger risk of oil spills and environmental pollution is expected in ice-covered seas. This research discipline address the effects of long-range transport of pollutants and their bioaccumulation in polar food chains, the influence of aerosols on the Earth's climate, the stratospheric ozone depletion and its effects on ecosystems and people in the Arctic and Antarctic, and the increased economic activity and related hazards.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Mark, Felix Christopher	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Both poles
Peters, Kimberley	UK	Helmholtz-Institut für Funktionelle Marine Biodiversität an der Universität Oldenburg (HIFMB)	Antarctic
Jiménez, Begoña	Spanish	IQOG-CSIC	Antarctic
Bastmeijer, Kees	Dutch	Universiy of Tilburg	Antarctic, Both poles
Paris, Jean-Daniel	French	CEA, LSCE, Saclay	Arctic
Heimburger, Lars-Eric	German	CNRS, MIO, Marseille	Arctic
Kangur Mihkel	Estonian	Tallinn University	Arctic
Zieger, Paul	German	Stockholm University	Arctic
Laudon, Hjalmar	Swedish	SLU	Arctic
Stedmon, Colin	Irish	Technical University of Denmark	Both poles
Merrild, Anne	Danish	Aalborg University/Greenland University	Arctic
Yilmaz, Atilla	Turkish	TUBITAK MAM Polar Research Institute	Antarctic
Lowther, Andrew	Australian / UK	Norwegian Polar Institute	Antarctic
Dodds, Klaus	UK	RH	TBA
Ademollo, Nicoletta	Italian	CNSR-ISP	Antarctic
Gilardoni, Stefania	Italian	CNR-ISP	Arctic
Fedchuk Andrii	Ukrainian	National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine	Antarctic

6. Solid Earth and its Interactions

There is already significant strategic and commercial interest in the marine and terrestrial geological and geothermal resources in the Arctic. An improved understanding of the distribution of these resources, would benefit both residents and stakeholders alike. Main objectives would thus address the strategic and commercial interest in Polar resources (mainly Arctic), and the scientific support of the definition of the exclusive economic zone in the Arctic.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Schindwein, Vera	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Arctic
Läufer, Andreas	German	Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources	Antarctic
Galindo-Zaldivar, Jesus	Spanish	IACT (CSIC- University of Granada)	Antarctic
Chambodut, Aude	French	Universite Strasbourg, ITES, Strasbourg	Both poles
Kusiak Monika	Polish	Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Sciences	Both poles
Soesoo Alvar	Estonian	University of Tartu	Both poles
Huybrechts Philippe	Belgian	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	Both poles
Debaille Vinciane	Belgian	Université Libre de Bruxelles	Antarctic
Rosing, Minik	Greenlandic	Univer'sity of Copenhagen	Arctic
Kjeldsen, Kjellerup, Kristian	Danish	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland	Both poles
Phillips Conrad, Clinton	USA	University of Oslo, Department of Geosciences, CoE Earth Evolution and Dynamics	Both poles
Crispini, Laura	Italian	UNIGE	Antarctic
Doveri, Marco	Italian	CNR-IGG	Arctic

7. Sustainable Management of Resources

Untapped global petroleum resources may be found in the high North, as well as significant fisheries resources, forests and mineral resources are to be found in the region. The effects of global warming would provide a better access to these resources, and this has significantly increased the interest in the region, by Arctic and non-Arctic states and international businesses. Therefore the main objectives would address the feasibility, challenges and impact of exploitation of Arctic petroleum resources (20 to 30 percent of the untapped global petroleum), the sustainable use of fisheries, forests and mineral resources in the Arctic, the impact of reduced sea-ice in relation to exploitation of Arctic oil and gas reserves, the impact of increased human/industrial activity on traditional lifestyles such as reindeer herding, and the pollution risks and risks to safe food and water supply.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Werner, Karl	German	Institute of Sea Fisheries	Arctic
Teschke, Katharina	German	Alfred Wegener Institute	Antarctic
Sarralde, Roberto	Spanish	IEO (Spanish Institute of Oceanography)	Antarctic
Sarkki, Simo	Finland	Cultural anthropology, University of Oulu, Finland	Arctic
Lamers, machiel	Dutch	Wageningen University	Antarctic
Gaillardet, Jerome	French	IPGP, Paris	Arctic
Thebaud, Olivier	French	IFREMER, AMURE, Plouzané	Both poles
Kruszewska Agnieszka	Polish	Institute of Biochemistry and Biophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences	Both poles
Skogrand, Pål Einar	Norwegian	Aker Biomarine AS	Antarctic
Merrild, Anne	Greenlandic	Aalborg University/Greenland University	Arctic
Ren, Carina	Danish	Aalborg University	Arctic
Lowther, Andy	Australian / United Kingdom	Norwegian Polar Institute	Antarctic
Fossheim, Maria	Norwegian	Institute of Marine Research (Tromsø, Norway)	Arctic
Hovelsrud, Grete K.	Norwegian	Nord University, Bodø, Norway	Arctic
Ghigliotti, Laura	Italian	CNR-ISMAR	Arctic
Schiaparelli, Stefano	Italian	UNIGE	Antarctic
Vishnyakova Karina	Ukrainian	National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine	Antarctic

8. People, Societies and Cultures

A number of rapid societal and environmental changes confront Arctic residents, local communities and socioeconomic sectors and challenge their livelihoods and well-being. Important trends are demographic shifts and urbanization, changing livelihoods and lifestyles, economic dependence on the primary sector and public transfers, the increasing role of education and research, empowerment and increasing complexity of governance. There is also a growing recognition of the importance of local and traditional knowledge to these societies. Therefore, the main objectives would address the changes in lifestyle of indigenous communities, alterations in family structure, values and cultural forms of expression, the increasing role of women in society, barriers to intergenerational knowledge transmission or loss of indigenous languages and cultural heritage management.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Manero-Salvador, Ana	Spanish	Associate Professor. University Carlos III of Madrid	Arctic
Conde, Elena	Spanish	Universidad Complutense de Madrid	Arctic
Kuokkanen, Rauna	Finland		Arctic
Desjardins, Sean	Canadian	University of Groningen - Arctic Centre	Arctic
Vaguet, Yvette	French	Université de Rouen, IDEES, Rouen	Arctic
COLLIGNON, Beatrice	French	Université de Bordeaux, PASSAGES, Bordeaux	Arctic
Skorupa Agnieszka	Polish	University of Silesia in Katowice	Both poles
Saxinger, Gertrude	Austrian	Austrian Polar Research Institute	Arctic
Schweitzer, Peter	Italian	University of Vienna, Austrian Polar Research Institute	Arctic
Ventsel Aimar	Estonian	University of Tartu	Arctic
Wood-Donnelly, Corine	USA	Uppsala University	Arctic
Benedicte Brincker	Danish	University of Copenhagen	Arctic
Koch Madsen, Christian	Danish	Greenland National Museum & Archives	Arctic
Dannevig, Halvor	Norwegian	Western Norway Research Institute	Arctic
Hovelsrud, Grete K.	Norwegian	Nord University, Bodø, Norway	Arctic
Soriani, Stefano	Italian	Ca-Foscari	Arctic

9. Human Health and Wellbeing

Changes in lifestyle, in combination with environmental and societal changes, have major impacts on the health and wellbeing of indigenous communities, while urban populations may be less affected. In terms of health, there is special concern in some Arctic counties over increases in cancer and other lifestyle-related diseases, sexually transmitted diseases, suicides and alcoholism. Main objectives would thus address changes in lifestyle impacting the health and wellbeing of indigenous communities, the impact of climate change and socio-economic changes on food, water and energy security, and changes in the rates of cancer and other lifestyle-related diseases, sexually transmitted diseases, suicides and alcoholism.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Rautio Arja	Finnish	University of Oulu	Arctic
Roza Laptander	Nenet	University Hamburg	Arctic
Robach, Paul	French	ENSA, Chamonix	Both poles
Szkarłat Monika	Polish	International Relations Department, Institute of Political Sciences and Administration, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Lublin, Poland	Arctic
Adams, Ria-Maria	Finland	University of Vienna	Arctic
Pattyn Nathalie	Belgian	Vrije universiteit Brussel	Both poles
Evengård, Birgitta	Swedish	Umeå University	Arctic
Nilsson. Lena Maria	Swedish/Same	Vardduo	Arctic
Jørgensen Eika, Marit	Danish	Steno Diabetes Centre, Greenland	Arctic
Billi, Daniela	Italian	UNIROMA3	Antarctic
Pasquali, Vittorio	Italian	UNIROMA1	Arctic

10. Astronomy, Astrophysics and Space

The Polar Regions provide an ideal platform from which to study the Earth's upper atmosphere, the solar system and outer space, to improve understanding of sun-earth connections and space-weather and answer fundamental questions such as the origin of the universe. Therefore, the main objectives would address the development of an ideal platform to study outer space, the development of prototypes and testing of equipment destined for space use, the forecast of space weather, and the identification of useful sites for observing Sun-Earth interactions.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Tanskanen, Eija	Finnish	Sodankylä Geophysical Observatory, University of Oulu	Both poles
Guillot, Tristan	French	CNRS, LAGRANGE, Nice	Both poles
Coude du Foresto, Vincent	French	Observatoire de Paris, LESIA, Meudon	Antarctic
Noorma Anu	Estonian	Tartu Observatory	Both poles
Bergeot Nicolas	Belgian	Royal Observatory Belgium	Arctic
Linden-Vørnle, Michael	Danish	Technical University of Denmark	Both poles
Forsberg, René	Danish	Technical University of Denmark	Both poles
Torta, J. Miquel	Spanish	Observatori de l'Ebre, CSIC - Univ. Ramon Llull	Both poles
Marcucci, Maria Federica	Italian	INAF	Antarctic
Alfonsi, Lucilla	Italian	INGV	Arctic
Koloskov Oleksandr	Ukrainian	State Institution National Antarctic Scientific Center MES of Ukraine, Institute of Radio Astronomy NAS of Ukraine	Arctic

11. New Technologies

This discipline is considered overarching and cross-cutting with all the other themes that they should be applied to most of the research questions of the above-mentioned disciplines.

Last name, first name	Nationality	Affiliation	Polar area
Hoving, Jeroen	Dutch	Delft University	Arctic
Weimerskirch, Henri	French	CNRS, CEBC, Villiers en bois	Both poles
Głowacki Piotr	Polish	Institute of Geophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences	Both poles
Kruusmaa Maarja	Estonian	Tallinn University of Technology	Arctic
Berte Johan	Belgian	AntarctiQ bv & Berte bv	Both poles
Tonboe, Rasmus	Danish	Danish Meteorological Institute	Arctic
Melvad, Claus	Danish	Aarhus University	Arctic
Løset, Sveinung	Norwegian	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Faculty of Engineering and Technology	Arctic
Rose, Mike	UK	BAS	TBA
Potenza, Marco	Italian	UNIMI	Antarctic
Vitale, Vito	Italian	CNR-ISP	Arctic

7. Statistics

Table 1: Gender distribution across all research disciplines.

Gender	Amount
Female	56
Male	103
Not disclosed	21
Sum Total	180

Figure 1 shows the gender distribution of the nominees across all research disciplines.

Table 2: National distribution across all research disciplines.

Nationality	Amount
Australian / United Kingdom	2
Austrian	1
Belgian	13
Canadian	2
Catalan (Spanish)	1
Danish	16
Dutch	8
Estonian	9
Finland	3
Finnish	4
French	17
German	17
Greenlandic	2
Irish	1
Italian	22
Nenet	1
Norwegian	12
Polish	11
Portuguese	2
Spanish	12
Swedish	8
Swedish/Dutch	1
Swedish/Same	1
Turkish	2
UK	4
Ukrainian	6
USA	2
Sum Total	180

Figure 2 displays the nationality distribution of the nominees irrespective of research discipline. The horizontal axis shows the amount of nominees, while the vertical axis shows nationalities.

Table 3: Polar area distribution of all nominees irrespective of research discipline.

Polar Area of Expertise	Nominees
Antarctic	38
Arctic	82
Both poles	57
Not disclosed	3
Sum Total	180

Figure 3 shows the Polar area distribution of the nominees irrespective of research discipline.